

Resurrection of All Humans

Optimistic, Realistic and Pessimistic Scenarios

1st Scenario: Optimistic (Medium Far)

-Resurrection of the First Human

Period of Time: Several Decades

-Resurrection of All Humans

Period of Time: Several Millenniums

2nd Scenario: Realistic (Far)

-Resurrection of the First Human

Period of Time: Several Centuries

-Resurrection of All Humans

Period of Time: Several Tens of Thousands of Years

3rd Scenario: Pessimistic (Very Far)

-Resurrection of the First Human

Period of Time: Several Millenniums

-Resurrection of All Humans

Period of Time: Several Hundreds of Thousands of Years

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